

Let's Break the Silence: Suicide in Prisons- Risk Factors, Epidemiology and Prevention

Sessizliği Yıkalm: Cezaevi İntiharları-Epidemiyoloji, Riskler ve Önleme

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Abstract

Suicide in prisons is a major public health and institutional concern. Incarcerated individuals face a much higher risk of suicide than the general population. This review synthesizes current literature on the epidemiology, psychosocial risk factors, and prevention of suicidal behavior among prisoners. It highlights the interplay between individual vulnerabilities (importation model) such as psychiatric disorders, past trauma, substance use, and social disadvantage and prison-specific stressors (deprivation model), including overcrowding, isolation, limited social contact, and strict disciplinary measures. Studies show that the early period of incarceration, especially the first days and weeks, is a critical window of heightened suicide risk due to adjustment difficulties, acute stress, and loss of social support. Effective prevention requires an integrated approach combining interventions for high-risk individuals, such as mental health screening, psychosocial support, trauma-informed therapy, and anger management, with broader strategies to improve prison conditions, enhance social connections, and foster a supportive environment. Strengthening family ties, promoting positive staff-inmate relationships, and providing educational, vocational, and recreational programs can further enhance resilience and reduce self-harm risk. Comprehensive strategies addressing both individual and environmental factors are essential to mitigate suicide risk. This review emphasizes the need for interdisciplinary, multi-level interventions for sustainable suicide prevention in correctional settings.

Keywords: Prison Suicide, Self-harm, Incarcerated, Risk Factors, Suicide Prevention.

Özet

Cezaevi intiharları hem halk sağlığı hem de kurumsal bir sorundur. Mahkûmlar, genel nüfusa kıyasla çok daha yüksek intihar riski altındadır. Bu derleme, mahkûmlar arasında intihar davranışının epidemiyolojisi, psikososyal risk faktörleri ve önleme stratejilerine ilişkin güncel literatürü özetlemektedir. Bireysel sorunlar (ithalat/taşıma modeli); psikiyatrik bozukluklar, geçmiş travmalar, madde kullanımı ve sosyal dezavantajlar ile cezaevine özgü stres faktörleri (yoksunluk modeli), örneğin aşırı kalabalık hücreler, izolasyon, sınırlı sosyal temas ve sıkı disiplin önlemleri arasındaki etkileşim vurgulanmaktadır. Araştırmalar, özellikle tutukluluğun ilk günleri ve haftalarının, uyum zorlukları, akut stres ve sosyal destek kaybı nedeniyle intihar riskinin en yüksek olduğu kritik bir dönem olduğunu göstermektedir. Etkili önleme, yüksek riskli bireyler için mental sağlık taramaları, psikososyal destek, travma odaklı terapi ve öfke kontrolü gibi müdahalelerle, cezaevi koşullarının iyileştirilmesi, sosyal bağlantıların güçlendirilmesi ve destekleyici bir ortamın oluşturulmasını birleştiren entegre bir yaklaşım gerektirir. Aile bağlarının güçlendirilmesi, olumlu personel-mahkûm ilişkilerinin teşvik edilmesi ve eğitim, mesleki ve rekreatif programların sunulması psikolojik dayanıklılığı artırabilir ve intihar ile kendine zarar verme riskini azaltabilir. Hem bireysel hem de çevresel faktörleri ele alan kapsamlı stratejiler, intihar riskini azaltmak için esastır. Bu derleme, cezaevlerinde sürdürülebilir intihar önleme için disiplinler arası ve çok düzeyli müdahalelerin önemini vurgulamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Cezaevi İntiharı, Kendine Zarar Verme, Mahkûm, Risk Faktörleri, İntiharı Önleme.

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Suicidal behavior, defined as an intentional self-directed act that may or may not result in death, has been increasing worldwide, with nearly 800,000 deaths by suicide reported each year. Epidemiological data show that suicide rates have risen by approximately 30% over the past two decades, making suicide the tenth leading cause of death across all age groups. Suicide is the most common cause of death among young people and the second leading cause of death among 15-29-year-olds, after traffic accidents and other unnatural causes (Fleischmann & De Leo, 2014; WHO, 2025). A previous suicide attempt is recognized as one of the strongest predictors of future suicidal behavior. Researches indicate that a significant proportion of individuals who engage in an initial suicide attempt are likely to repeat such behavior within the following year, with some studies reporting recurrence rates approaching 50% (Bostwick et al., 2016; Schmidtke et al., 1996). This highlights the importance of understanding suicidal behavior not merely as an isolated psychological crisis, but as a complex phenomenon emerging from the interaction of multiple personal, social, and environmental risk factors.

Suicide rates in prisons are considerably higher than in the general population. Life in prisons is shaped by various social, psychological, and environmental factors that create significant risks to inmates' mental health. Researches indicate that suicide behavior among male inmates is three to eight times higher than in general population, while among female inmates it is ten times higher (Fazel et al., 2017). Approximately 80 % of prisoners are reported to be at significant risk of suicide (Görgülü & Tutarel-Kışlak, 2014). This risk is particularly elevated during the initial days of incarceration.

Considering the psychosocial risks within prisons, it is estimated that approximately 10% of inmates engage in at least one self-harming behavior during their incarceration (Favril et al., 2022). This phenomenon can be linked to individual-level psychiatric and social factors such as depression, anxiety, substance use, past trauma, limited social support, and loneliness (Angelakis et al., 2020b; Görgülü & Tutarel-Kışlak, 2014). At the institutional level,

environmental conditions including single-cell confinement, restricted visitation opportunities, lack of meaningful activities, and absence of privacy also contribute to the occurrence of such behaviors (Huey & McNulty, 2005; Larney & Farrell, 2017).

The existing literature indicates that the phenomenon of suicide in prisons has been predominantly studied in high-income countries. In contrast, systematic and comparable data from low- and middle-income regions remain scarce (Fazel et al., 2011; Mundt & Baggio, 2024). This gap hinders the development of effective suicide prevention strategies at both national and global levels. Effective interventions should not be limited to individual psychological support and treatment. They should also include staff training, risk assessment systems, improvements in prison conditions, and the strengthening of social support networks. Limited access to mental health services and structural challenges in many countries, including Türkiye, pose additional obstacles to these initiatives. Therefore, preventing suicide in prisons should be approached as a multidimensional process requiring interdisciplinary collaboration and comprehensive institutional interventions. Within this context, the present study examines the definition of suicidal behavior, epidemiological findings, and key suicide risk factors in prisons, while offering recommendations for effective and sustainable prison suicide prevention policies.

Suicide Risk Factors in Prisons

Prison suicide is one of the most significant mental health challenges faced by correctional systems worldwide. International data indicate that the risk of suicide among inmates is 5-10 times higher than in the general population (Bachmann, 2018). The initial days of detention are particularly critical, representing the period of the highest risk (Radeloff et al., 2021). Two main approaches have been proposed to understand this risk. Those are the Importation Model and Deprivation Model. These models represent two fundamental theoretical perspectives on the patterns of response to imprisonment (Schwartz, 1971; Thomas & Foster, 1973). The Importation Model focuses on individual characteristics and psychiatric factors from a psychological and public health perspective, while the Deprivation Model

emphasizes the negative conditions created by the prison environment from a sociological and criminological perspective. The psychological perspective identifies factors such as depression, anxiety, substance use, trauma history, and genetic vulnerability as key contributors to suicide risk. In contrast, the sociological approach highlights that inmates often come from disadvantaged social backgrounds. Adverse prison conditions, such as overcrowded cells, social isolation, limited communication, and strict disciplinary measures, increase psychological pressure and can trigger suicidal behavior. The two principal theoretical approaches explaining suicide in prisons are examined in the following sections.

Importation Model: Psychological and Public Health Perspective

Within the framework of the Importation Model, inmates already possess certain risk factors before entering prison. Suicidal behavior, in this context, is largely independent of the prison environment and is primarily associated with pre-existing psychological conditions and social disadvantages. In other words, these individuals represent a high-risk and socially disadvantaged population. Considering the widespread prevalence of mental disorders and various psychosocial difficulties among prisoners, the Importation Model emphasizes the importance of identifying and addressing these vulnerabilities early in the incarceration process (Molina-Coloma et al., 2021). The Importation Model offers a compelling and coherent explanatory framework for understanding suicide in correctional settings. In this context, the risk factors emphasized by this model are as follows:

Suicide ideation, self-harm and suicide attempts

Among the strongest predictors of suicidal behavior are suicidal ideation, a history of self-harm, and previous suicide attempts (Liu et al., 2022). Suicidal thoughts that involve planning and concrete preparations represent the most critical risk factors for suicidal behavior, particularly when accompanied by feelings of hopelessness and helplessness (Bauer et al., 2022; Görgülü, 2020). In prison populations, this risk is significantly higher compared to the general population. Approximately 33% of prisoners report suicidal ideation, while 9% have made at least one attempt during incarceration. Suicide attempt rates are 12.2% among

men and 8.6% among women in prisons (Favril et al., 2020; Favril et al., 2022). Furthermore, 19-22% of incarcerated individuals have attempted suicide at some point in their lives which is a high risk for suicide. The risk is particularly elevated in the initial weeks of imprisonment due to acute stress and adjustment difficulties (Radeloff et al., 2021), with suicide rates reaching nearly 10 times higher than those of the population.

Psychiatric disorders

Psychiatric disorders are among the most significant determinants of high-risk behaviors, with mood disorders representing particularly strong predictors. Major depression and bipolar disorder are frequently linked to an increased risk of suicide, with approximately 15% of individuals with depression exhibiting related high-risk behaviors, and 50-60% of those who died by suicide having a history of major depressive disorder (Angst et al., 1999; Jeon, 2011). In Canadian correctional facilities, the lifetime prevalence of depression among prisoners ranges from 21.5% to 29.8% (Boothby & Durham, 1999). Substance use disorders further amplify this risk, particularly when co-occurring with depressive symptoms. Nearly half of the individuals who died by suicide were reported to have a history of substance use (Schneider, 2009). Among inmates, substance use is highly prevalent, with tobacco use reported in 72%, alcohol use in 26-39%, and illicit drug use in 64% of individuals (Butler et al., 2003). Borderline Personality Disorder, characterized by emotional dysregulation, impulsivity, and fear of abandonment, is also a significant risk factor, with 9-33% of affected individuals having engaged in high-risk behaviors at least once in their lifetime. In prison populations, the prevalence of psychiatric disorders is markedly higher than in the general population. Conditions such as depression, bipolar disorder, substance use disorders, and borderline personality disorder occur several times more frequently among inmates (Armoon et al., 2021; Mundt & Baggio, 2024). The high prevalence of these psychiatric and substance-related conditions contributes substantially to the elevated incidence of high-risk behaviors within correctional settings.

Neglect and abuse

A considerable proportion of offenders have experienced such adversities during childhood and adolescence, which are widely recognized as major contributors to long-term psychosocial difficulties (Angelakis et al., 2020b; Capuzzi et al., 2021). Empirical evidence consistently demonstrates that early traumatic experiences, particularly recurrent abuse, undermine self-concept and foster feelings of worthlessness, guilt, and helplessness, thereby increasing vulnerability to both criminal and self-destructive behaviors (Angelakis et al., 2020a; Kaplan et al., 1997). Emotional and behavioral problems commonly observed among trauma survivors, such as anger, impulsivity, and aggression, may further facilitate criminal involvement and elevate the risk of self-harm. The prison environment intensifies this vulnerability, as isolation, punitive conditions, and limited social ties often reactivate earlier feelings of insecurity and helplessness (Armour, 2012). For inmates without adequate family or social support, these conditions may erode coping capacities and increase susceptibility to self-injurious or suicidal behaviors, positioning childhood trauma as a critical determinant of both offending and suicide risk.

Physical and mental health problems

Chronic illnesses and infectious diseases, such as HIV and hepatitis C, occur at rates of 5-10% among prisoners, substantially higher than in the general population (Weyant et al., 2023). Psychiatric disorders and substance use are also widespread among inmates, and the prevalence of these problems is significantly higher than in the general population. The combination of social disadvantage and health problems makes prisoners more psychologically vulnerable and less able to cope with stress. This underscores the urgent need for comprehensive interventions at multiple levels, including improvements in education, social support, healthcare access, and living conditions within prisons.

Social factors and health problems

One of the risk factors for the Importation Model is social factors and health problems among prisoners. Prisons predominantly house socioeconomically disadvantaged and

vulnerable individuals. Around 60% of inmates have not completed high school (Harlow, 2003), while in the United Kingdom, over 30% enter prison living at or near the poverty line, and nearly 20% of prisoners in several countries lack stable housing prior to incarceration (Greenberg & Rosenheck, 2008). These negative factors represent key structural vulnerabilities for inmates.

Deprivation Model: Structural and Institutional Risk Factors

The elevated risk of suicide among incarcerated individuals is shaped not only by pre-existing psychopathological vulnerabilities or adverse life experiences prior to imprisonment but also by the structural and social conditions within correctional facilities. Empirical research highlights that suicide in prisons is a multidimensional phenomenon, arising from the dynamic interplay between individual susceptibilities and environmental stressors inherent in institutional contexts (Mazher & Arai, 2025).

The Deprivation Model has been widely used to explain these institutional influences, emphasizing that solitary confinement, restricted social support, high-security environments, and the intake process significantly increase suicide risk (Thomas, 1977). According to this model, the loss of autonomy combined with deprivation of fundamental human needs, such as freedom, safety, privacy, and meaningful social interaction, can produce profound and enduring psychological consequences (Hayes, 1995). Newly admitted inmates are particularly vulnerable, as they are often separated from family, lose prior social supports, and experience abrupt disruptions to their daily routines. These deprivations undermine social identity, belonging, and self-worth, and research indicates that such restrictions are strongly associated with heightened depressive affect and increased susceptibility to suicidal behavior (Miller, 1994). Environmental stressors commonly observed in prisons, such as overcrowded cells, excessive noise, lack of privacy, and limited physical space, further strain psychological resilience and intensify mental health difficulties. In addition, the absence of meaningful activities and restricted opportunities for social engagement can exacerbate feelings of boredom, helplessness, and despair. Chronic stress, adaptation challenges, and emotional

exhaustion within the prison context are consistently identified as some of the most significant institutional determinants of suicide (Huey & McNulty, 2005). High-security facilities are particularly concerning, as the combination of strict routines, continuous surveillance, and reduced autonomy amplifies social isolation and psychological strain.

Moreover, the prison intake process itself constitutes a critical period of vulnerability. During the initial days and weeks of incarceration, inmates frequently experience shock, anxiety, uncertainty, and disorientation (D'Orta et al., 2022; Reinhardt & Rogers, 1998). These conditions can precipitate acute psychological distress, especially for individuals with pre-existing mental health issues or prior trauma exposure. Limited access to social support during this period can further compromise coping capacity, increasing the likelihood of self-harm or suicidal behavior (Radeloff et al., 2021).

Prison intake process and maladjustment

The initial period of incarceration constitutes a critical high-risk phase for inmates and is frequently associated with elevated suicide risk. Newly admitted individuals experience not only the loss of personal freedom but also heightened uncertainty, fear, and anxiety regarding their immediate and future circumstances. During this period, intense emotional reactions such as shock, anger, helplessness, and acute distress are common and may increase susceptibility to self-harming behaviors (Hayes, 1995).

Adjustment challenges are compounded by unfamiliarity with institutional rules, procedures, and social dynamics, as well as the need to navigate a novel and often stressful environment. These factors contribute to heightened psychological vulnerability, with the first weeks of incarceration representing a particularly high-risk for suicide ideation and suicidal behavior (Radeloff et al., 2021). Given these risks, the implementation of structured psychosocial support programs for newly admitted inmates is essential (Calear et al., 2016). Such programs should provide orientation to institutional routines, deliver emotional and social support, and facilitate the development of adaptive coping strategies. Interventions may include mentorship schemes, group therapy sessions, and regular psychological counseling,

all designed to enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability. A robust intake support framework enables early identification of high-risk individuals, facilitates adaptation to the prison environment, and ensures rapid intervention in crisis situations. Accordingly, targeted measures during the intake process play a pivotal role in mitigating suicide risk at both the individual and institutional levels.

Lack of social support and effect of social isolation

One of the most critical predictors of suicidal behavior is the weakness of social support mechanisms. Social support not only fulfills individuals' emotional needs but also strengthens their capacity to cope with stress, thereby serving as a protective buffer against adverse life events (Hou et al., 2022). Within prison settings, the weakening of ties with family members and social networks often intensifies feelings of loneliness and helplessness. In particular, inmates who lack support systems or who have fragile family relationships are at greater risk for suicide (Marzano et al., 2016).

In correctional environments, social support extends beyond family and peer relationships. Interactions with prison staff also constitute an essential component of this process. Experiencing acceptance and fair treatment from staff can enhance inmates' sense of self-worth. Conversely, being subjected to exclusion, belittlement, arbitrary disciplinary practices, or hostile attitudes can foster feelings of worthlessness and hopelessness, thereby elevating suicide risk. Research indicates that supportive staff attitudes mitigate loneliness, enhance self-esteem, and contribute to the development of psychological resilience among inmates (Marzano et al., 2016; Pratt & Foster, 2020). Therefore, strengthening social support systems in prisons depends not only on maintaining family connections but also on fostering more constructive and positive relationships between inmates and correctional staff. Initiatives such as encouraging family visits, expanding opportunities for communication with the outside world, and training prison staff in psychosocial support are considered vital protective measures for reducing suicide risk.

Solitary confinement and its psychological consequences

One of the most critical institutional factors that heighten the risk of suicide in prisons is the use of solitary confinement. Solitary confinement entails severely restricting an inmate's physical and social contact with others. Prolonged placement in single cells deprives individuals of both sensory and social stimulation, leading to profound psychological consequences. In the short term, such conditions may manifest as acute anxiety, panic attacks, restlessness, and sleep disturbances. In the long term, they may progress to severe depression, cognitive impairments, psychotic symptoms, and suicide ideation (Grassi et al., 2018; Hayes, 1995). Thus, solitary confinement should not be regarded merely as a disciplinary or security measure but rather as a high-risk practice that undermines psychological integrity and can precipitate suicidal behavior (Bonner, 2006).

Extended isolation, in particular, disrupts an individual's perception of time, erodes social skills, and reinforces feelings of helplessness. For this reason, many experts argue that solitary confinement should be conceptualized not only as a disciplinary tool but also as a form of psychological torture. Empirical research consistently demonstrates that inmates held under solitary conditions face a suicide risk several times higher than that observed in the general prison population. These findings underscore the urgent need to reconsider correctional policies within the framework of suicide prevention (Maszak-Prato & Graham, 2022; Morgan et al., 2016).

High-security prisons and structural risk factors

High-security prisons are the correctional settings where the risk of suicide is greatest. Strict disciplinary rules, constant monitoring, and severe restrictions on social interaction in these facilities have a strong negative impact on inmates' mental health. Prisoners placed in high-security units are usually those convicted of serious crimes, individuals with violent tendencies, or inmates with frequent disciplinary problems. At the same time, these groups often suffer from serious psychological difficulties and face an increased risk of suicide (Şenol, 2003). In such institutions, ties with the outside world become weak, visitation rights

are limited, and opportunities for social contact are kept to a minimum. This intense isolation can be especially harmful for inmates with a history of traumatic experiences, as it may recreate or intensify past trauma. Feelings of loneliness, helplessness, and loss of control become more pronounced in these settings, which in turn raise vulnerability to depression, anxiety, and suicidal thoughts (Maszak-Prato & Graham, 2022; Morgan et al., 2016). Because of these elevated risks, suicide prevention and self-harm reduction efforts should be given high priority and applied more effectively in high-security prisons.

Type of Crime and Suicide

It is difficult to argue that the relationship between crime types and suicidal behavior can be defined in direct and clear terms. Although research has examined the effects of different crime types on suicide risk, the findings are not always consistent. Since suicidal behavior emerges through the interaction of multidimensional psychological, social, and environmental factors, explaining it solely by the type of crime committed offers only a limited perspective. Nevertheless, when violent crimes are considered, stronger associations with suicidal behavior appear more frequently (Cook, 2012). Suicidal behavior can essentially be defined as an act of violence directed toward oneself, and therefore, it is not surprising that individuals convicted of violent offenses are at greater risk of self-directed violence. Research has shown that individuals convicted of serious violent crimes such as assault, homicide, and sexual violence display higher levels of suicidal behavior compared to those involved in other crime categories (Cook, 2013; Larney et al., 2012). This finding suggests that violent crimes not only pose harm to victims but may also constitute a potential threat to the perpetrator's own life.

When examining the personality traits of individuals convicted of violent crimes, tendencies such as impulsivity, poor anger control, and aggressiveness are strongly associated with both outwardly directed violence and self-harming behavior (Tharshini et al., 2021). In this regard, it can be argued that outward aggression and inward destructive behaviors share common psychological processes. Indeed, compared to other offender groups, violent

offenders are more likely to choose highly lethal and painful suicide methods such as hanging, strangulation, or firearm use (Webb et al., 2013). However, the relationship between violent behavior and suicide is not limited to personality traits. Long prison sentences, social stigma, feelings of remorse and guilt, and lack of social support are also important psychosocial factors that increase the suicide risk in this group. Thus, aggression should be understood not only as an outwardly directed behavioral pattern but also as an inward form of self-destruction. This highlights that individuals convicted of violent crimes are at a heightened risk of harming both others and themselves, underscoring the need for this group to be addressed specifically in suicide prevention efforts.

Prevention of Suicide in Prisons

Prison suicides are considered not only as an individual problem but also as a serious public health and institutional security concern. Therefore, efforts to prevent suicide in correctional settings are critical. Prisoners face higher levels of psychological difficulties compared to the general population, and these psychosocial problems are closely associated with self-harm and suicidal behavior (Armoon et al., 2021; Butler et al., 2003). In this context, self-harming behaviors are commonly reported among prisoners and may occasionally function as a strategy to seek attention from staff or influence institutional responses. Unfortunately, this situation sometimes leads to suicide attempts being perceived as manipulative behaviors, which can cause prisoners with genuine suicidal intent to be overlooked. However, evidence clearly shows that suicide rates in prisons are significantly higher than in the general population, highlighting the urgent need for effective prevention strategies. Factors such as psychosocial deprivation, isolation, past trauma, and limited access to support mechanisms are among the main contributors to suicide risk in correctional settings.

Preventing suicide in prisons begins with identifying risk factors before incarceration. Childhood trauma, histories of neglect or abuse, behavioral disorders, family problems, past suicide attempt and social or academic difficulties are important risk indicators that should be

assessed (Angelakis et al., 2020b; Capuzzi et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022). Individuals with severe traumatic histories often struggle with anger regulation and impulsive behaviors, which increases the likelihood of self-directed violence (Kaplan et al., 1997; Tharshini et al., 2021). Therefore, close monitoring of prisoners with anger management problems or a history of violent offenses is a critical step in preventing prison suicides.

Once incarcerated, reducing suicide risk requires continuous monitoring and psychosocial support. Prisoners with serious psychological problems and those identified as high-risk should be systematically assessed, closely observed, and regularly followed up. Nevertheless, focusing only on treatment may not be sufficient. Rehabilitation and prevention programs must also be implemented in parallel. Improving prison conditions plays an essential role in enhancing the effectiveness of suicide prevention. Structural measures such as reducing overcrowding, protecting prisoners' privacy, and minimizing social isolation represent crucial structural interventions (Favril, 2021).

At the same time, strengthening social support mechanisms is vital in reducing suicide risk. Research shows that prisoners with weaker social support networks have a higher likelihood of self-harm and suicidal behavior (Marzano et al., 2016). Therefore, facilitating regular contact with family members, expanding communication opportunities, and maintaining ties with the outside world are important protective factors. Similarly, positive and supportive relationships with prison staff help prisoners feel valued, foster a sense of belonging, and contribute to the development of psychological resilience.

Additional preventive strategies include education, vocational training, group therapy, trauma-focused interventions, and anger management programs, all of which have been found to reduce the risk of self-harm and suicide (Stephenson et al., 2021). Furthermore, constructive activities such as art, sports, and other meaningful engagements can strengthen prisoners' self-esteem, promote a sense of purpose, and nurture hope for the future, thereby serving as effective protective factors against suicide.

Conclusion

This study highlights that suicide in prisons is a complex and urgent issue, carrying substantial implications for both public health and institutional safety. Suicide risk among incarcerated populations cannot be attributed to a single risk factor but emerges from the interaction of pre-existing vulnerabilities and prison-specific stressors. Childhood trauma, psychiatric disorders, substance use, and violent tendencies place many individuals at high risk even before incarceration. Once imprisoned, these vulnerabilities are compounded by institutional conditions such as overcrowding, social isolation, solitary confinement, and restricted social support, all of which intensify psychological distress and increase the likelihood of self-harm and suicide.

Theoretical models such as the importation and deprivation perspectives highlight the need for an integrated approach that considers both individual and structural risk factors. Prevention efforts should therefore begin prior to incarceration, with early identification of at-risk individuals and targeted interventions addressing trauma, mental health, and social disadvantage. After imprisonment, effective suicide prevention requires systematic risk assessment, continuous monitoring, and psychosocial support tailored to high-risk individuals. Moreover, strengthening social support networks emerges as a particularly protective factor. Facilitating family visits, enhancing communication with the outside world, and fostering supportive staff-inmate relationships can reduce feelings of isolation and promote resilience.

Ultimately, suicide prevention in prisons must be recognized as a multidimensional and interdisciplinary process. Collaborative efforts involving mental health professionals, correctional staff, policymakers, and community stakeholders are essential to developing sustainable strategies. By addressing both individual vulnerabilities and institutional stressors, correctional systems can significantly reduce suicide risk and improve the overall well-being of incarcerated individuals.

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References

- Angelakis, I., Austin, J. L., & Gooding, P. (2020a). Association of childhood maltreatment with suicide behaviors among young people: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Network Open*, 3(8), e2012563-e2012563.
- Angelakis, I., Austin, J. L., & Gooding, P. (2020b). Childhood maltreatment and suicide attempts in prisoners: a systematic meta-analytic review. *Psychological Medicine*, 50(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291719002848>
- Angst, J., Angst, F., & Stassen, H. H. (1999). Suicide risk in patients with major depressive disorder. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 60(2), 57-62.
- Armoon, B., SoleimanvandiAzar, N., Fleury, M.-J., Noroozi, A., Bayat, A.-H., Mohammadi, R., Ahounbar, E., & Fattah Moghaddam, L. (2021). Prevalence, sociodemographic variables, mental health condition, and type of drug use associated with suicide behaviors among people with substance use disorders: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Addictive Diseases*, 39(4), 550-569. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/10550887.2021.1912572>
- Armour, C. (2012). Mental health in prison: A trauma perspective on importation and deprivation. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociological Theory*, 5(2), 886-894.
- Bachmann, S. (2018). Epidemiology of suicide and the psychiatric perspective. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(7), 1425. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15071425>
- Bauer, B. W., Hom, M. A., Karnick, A. T., Charpentier, C. J., Keefer, L. A., Capron, D. W., Rudd, M. D., & Bryan, C. J. (2022). Does hopelessness accurately predict how bad you will feel in the future? Initial evidence of affective forecasting errors in individuals with elevated suicide risk. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 46(4), 686-703. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-021-10285-7>
- Bonner, R. L. (2006). Stressful segregation housing and psychosocial vulnerability in prison suicide ideators. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 36(2), 250-254.
- Boothby, J. L., & Durham, T. W. (1999). Screening for depression in prisoners using the Beck Depression Inventory. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 26(1), 107-124. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854899026001>
- Bostwick, J. M., Pabbati, C., Geske, J. R., & McKean, A. J. (2016). Suicide attempt as a risk factor for completed suicide: even more lethal than we knew. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 173(11), 1094-1100.
- Butler, T., Levy, M., Dolan, K., & Kaldor, J. (2003). Drug use and its correlates in an Australian prisoner population. *Addiction Research & Theory*, 11(2), 89-101. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/1606635021000021403>
- Calcar, A. L., Christensen, H., Freeman, A., Fenton, K., Busby Grant, J., Van Spijker, B., & Donker, T. (2016). A systematic review of psychosocial suicide prevention interventions for youth. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 25(5), 467-482. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-015-0783-4>
- Capuzzi, E., Caldiroli, A., Besana, F., Tagliabue, I., Capellazzi, M., Cova, F., Rubelli, P., Sergio, M. R., Truisi, E., & Buoli, M. (2021). The association between childhood trauma and lifetime suicide attempts among a sample of male prisoners: A pilot observational study. *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine*, 80, 102180. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jflm.2021.102180>
- Cook, T. B. (2012). Assessing legal strains and risk of suicide using archived court data. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 42(5), 495-506. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1943-278X.2012.00107.x>

- Cook, T. B. (2013). Recent criminal offending and suicide attempts: A national sample. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 48(5), 767-774. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-012-0567-9>
- D'Orta, I., Guilbert, N., Pierrard, M., Herrmann, F. R., & Giannakopoulos, P. (2022). Detained persons incarcerated for the first time and needing acute psychiatric care: Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13, 904735. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2022.904735>
- Favril, L. (2021). Epidemiology, risk factors, and prevention of suicidal thoughts and behaviour in prisons: A literature review. *Psychologica Belgica*, 61(1), 341.
- Favril, L., O'Connor, R. C., Hawton, K., & Vander Laenen, F. (2020). Factors associated with the transition from suicidal ideation to suicide attempt in prison. *European Psychiatry*, 63(1), e101.
- Favril, L., Shaw, J., & Fazel, S. (2022). Prevalence and risk factors for suicide attempts in prison. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 97, 102190.
- Fazel, S., Grann, M., Kling, B., & Hawton, K. (2011). Prison suicide in 12 countries: an ecological study of 861 suicides during 2003–2007. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 46(3), 191-195.
- Fazel, S., Ramesh, T., & Hawton, K. (2017). Suicide in prisons: an international study of prevalence and contributory factors. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 4(12), 946-952. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-010-0184-4>
- Fleischmann, A., & De Leo, D. (2014). The World Health Organization's report on suicide. *Crisis*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1027/0227-5910/a000293>
- Görgülü, T. (2020). Suicide Attempts among Male Prisoners with Substance Use and Non-Users: The Role of Depression and Hopelessness. *Yeni Symposium*, 58(4), 9-14. <https://doi.org/10.5455/NYS.20200709044345>
- Görgülü, T., & Tutarel-Kışlak, Ş. (2014). Submissive behaviour, depression, and suicide probability in male arrestees and convicts. *Nöro Psikiyatri Arşivi*, 51(1), 40-45. <https://doi.org/10.4274/npa.y6563>
- Grassi, S., Mandarelli, G., Polacco, M., Vetrugno, G., Spagnolo, A. G., & De-Giorgio, F. (2018). Suicide of isolated inmates suffering from psychiatric disorders: when a preventive measure becomes punitive. *International Journal of Legal Medicine*, 132(4), 1225-1230. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s00414-017-1704-5>
- Greenberg, G. A., & Rosenheck, R. A. (2008). Homelessness in the state and federal prison population. *Criminal Behaviour and Mental Health*, 18(2), 88-103. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/cbm.685>
- Harlow, C. W. (2003). Education and Correctional Populations. Bureau of Justice Statistics Special Report.
- Hayes, L. M. (1995). Prison suicide: An overview and a guide to prevention. *The Prison Journal*, 75(4), 431-456. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/00328555950750040>
- Hou, X., Wang, J., Guo, J., Zhang, X., Liu, J., Qi, L., & Zhou, L. (2022). Methods and efficacy of social support interventions in preventing suicide: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Ment Health*, 25(1), 29-35. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1136/ebmental-2021-300318>
- Huey, M. P., & McNulty, T. L. (2005). Institutional conditions and prison suicide: Conditional effects of deprivation and overcrowding. *The Prison Journal*, 85(4), 490-514. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/0032885505282258>
- Jeon, H. J. (2011). Depression and suicide. *Journal of the Korean Medical Association*, 54(4), 370-375. <https://doi.org/10.5124/jkma.2011.54.4.370>
- Kaplan, S. J., Pelcovitz, D., Salzinger, S., Mandel, F., & Weiner, M. (1997). Adolescent physical abuse and suicide attempts. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 36(6), 799-808.
- Larney, S., & Farrell, M. (2017). Prisoner suicide: A multilevel problem. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 4(12), 894-895.
- Larney, S., Topp, L., Indig, D., O'driscoll, C., & Greenberg, D. (2012). A cross-sectional survey of prevalence and correlates of suicidal ideation and suicide attempts among prisoners in New South Wales, Australia. *BMC Public Health*, 12(1), 14. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-12-14>
- Liu, B.-P., Jia, C.-X., Qin, P., Zhang, Y.-Y., Yu, Y.-K., Luo, X., & Li, S.-X. (2022). Associating factors of suicide and repetition following self-harm: a systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *EClinicalMedicine*, 49.

- Marzano, L., Hawton, K., Rivlin, A., Smith, E. N., Piper, M., & Fazel, S. (2016). Prevention of suicidal behavior in prisons. *Crisis*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1027/0227-5910/a000394>
- Maszak-Prato, S., & Graham, L. (2022). Reducing the Use of Segregation for People with Serious Mental Illness. *The Prison Journal*, 102(3), 283-303. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/00328855221095>
- Mazher, S., & Arai, T. (2025). Behind Bars: A Trauma-Informed Examination of Mental Health through Importation and Deprivation in Prisons. *European Journal of Trauma & Dissociation*, 100516.
- Miller, H. A. (1994). Reexamining psychological distress in the current conditions of segregation. *Journal of Correctional Health Care*, 1(2), 39-53. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/10783458940010020>
- Molina-Coloma, V., Lara-Machado, R., Pérez-Pedraza, B., & López-Rodríguez, D. (2021). Psychological symptomatology in a prison population: an exploratory study of age, psychopathological history and time in prison. *Revista Española de Sanidad Penitenciaria*, 23(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.18176/resp.00027>
- Morgan, R. D., Gendreau, P., Smith, P., Gray, A. L., Labrecque, R. M., MacLean, N., Van Horn, S. A., Bolanos, A. D., Batastini, A. B., & Mills, J. F. (2016). Quantitative syntheses of the effects of administrative segregation on inmates' well-being. *Psychology, Public Policy, and Law*, 22(4), 439. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1037/law0000089>
- Mundt, A. P., & Baggio, S. (2024). The central role of borderline personality disorder in imprisoned people: a network analysis of mental disorder diagnoses. *The Journal of Forensic Psychiatry & Psychology*, 35(3), 495-506. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2018.03.007>
- Pratt, D., & Foster, E. (2020). Feeling hopeful: can hope and social support protect prisoners from suicide ideation? *The Journal of Forensic Psychiatry & Psychology*, 31(2), 311-330. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/14789949.2020.1732445>
- Radeloff, D., Ten Hövel, M., Brennecke, G., Stoeber, F. S., Lempp, T., Kettner, M., Zacher, H., von Klitzing, K., & Bennefeld-Kersten, K. (2021). Suicide after reception into prison: a case-control study examining differences in early and late events. *Plos One*, 16(8), e0255284. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0255284>
- Reinhardt, V., & Rogers, R. (1998). Differences in anxiety between first-time and multiple-time inmates: a multicultural perspective. *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law Online*, 26(3), 375-382.
- Schmidtke, A., Bille-Brahe, U., DeLeo, D., Kerkhof, A., Bjerke, T., Crepief, P., Haring, C., Hawton, K., Lönnqvist, J., & Michel, K. (1996). Attempted suicide in Europe: rates, trend, S and sociodemographic characteristics of suicide attempters during the period 1989–1992. Results of the WHO/EURO Multicentre Study on Parasuicide. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 93(5), 327-338.
- Schneider, B. (2009). Substance use disorders and risk for completed suicide. *Archives of suicide research*, 13(4), 303-316. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/1381110903263191>
- Schwartz, B. (1971). Pre-institutional vs. situational influence in a correctional community. *The Journal of Criminal Law, Criminology, and Police Science*, 62(4), 532-542. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/1141708>
- Stephenson, T., Leaman, J., O'Moore, É., Tran, A., & Plugge, E. (2021). Time out of cell and time in purposeful activity and adverse mental health outcomes amongst people in prison: a literature review. *International Journal of Prisoner Health*, 17(1), 54-68. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPH-06-2020-0037>
- Şenol, E. (2003). *The situational and the personality factors predicting depression and anxiety of prisoners* [Middle East Technical University].
- Tharshini, N., Ibrahim, F., Kamaluddin, M. R., Rathakrishnan, B., & Che Mohd Nasir, N. (2021). The link between individual personality traits and criminality: A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(16), 8663. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18168663>
- Thomas, C. W. (1977). Theoretical perspectives on prisonization: A comparison of the importation and deprivation models. *Journal of Criminal Law & Criminology*, 68, 135.
- Thomas, C. W., & Foster, S. C. (1973). The importation model perspective on inmate social roles: An empirical test. *The Sociological Quarterly*, 14(2), 226-234. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1533-8525.1973.tb00855.x>

- Webb, R. T., Qin, P., Stevens, H., Shaw, J., Appleby, L., & Mortensen, P. (2013). National study of suicide method in violent criminal offenders. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 150*(2), 237-244. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2013.04.001>
- Weyant, C., Lee, S., Andrews, J. R., Alarid-Escudero, F., & Goldhaber-Fiebert, J. D. (2023). Dynamics of respiratory infectious diseases in incarcerated and free-living populations: a simulation modeling study. *Medical Decision Making, 43*(1), 42-52. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/0272989X22111536>
- WHO. (2025). *Suicide worldwide in 2021: global health estimates*. World Health Organization.